

Detecting floating stanzas in premodern Dutch songs

“*Floating stanzas*” are stanzas that recur in two or more songs that are otherwise seemingly unrelated (Grijp, 1991). While earlier scholarship has identified examples of such textual migrations in early Dutch song (Grijp, 1991, 2008), the scale, mechanisms and underlying motivations of this phenomenon remain insufficiently understood. This project addresses this gap by developing and applying computational methods to detect floating stanzas across the Dutch Song Database, thereby producing the first systematic mapping of textual reuse within the corpus of premodern Dutch song. The resulting dataset will subsequently be analyzed from four perspectives: the distribution of floating stanzas, their thematic content, the co-occurrence of multiple floating stanzas within individual songs and variation across attestations of the same stanza.

The *Dutch Song Database* is uniquely suited for this investigation. It contains nearly all monophonic Dutch songs prior to 1600, along with extensive seventeenth- and eighteenth-century material (Van Kranenburg et al., 2019). More importantly, its structured clustering of songs with shared texts and melodies provides a foundation for studying the transmission of songs (see e.g. Houtsma, 2012; Van Kranenburg et al., 2019; De Koninck, 2023). To date, however, the database has not been leveraged to analyze textual mobility at the level of individual stanzas. This study draws on existing computational methods for intertextuality detection in order to uncover patterns of textual dissemination in early modern song culture.

Nantke (2024) distinguishes between two dominant approaches within the computational detection of intertextuality: *text reuse detection*, which identifies literal textual correspondences, and *semantic similarity detection*, which captures conceptual parallels even when wording diverges. This project compares algorithms from both approaches, recognizing that floating stanzas range from verbatim repetition – potentially including spelling variation – to paraphrased variants shaped by both oral and written transmission.

This lightning talk presents the first stage within this research project, comparing four algorithms previously used in literary text reuse detection on a training corpus of floating stanzas derived from the critical edition of the *Antwerp songbook* (Van der Poel et al., 2004). Two of these methods are lemma-based, namely TF-IDF scoring with additional weighting for rhyme words (Kestemont, 2025) and character n-gram overlap. The remaining two methods are semantic, using Latent Semantic Indexing (Arévalo, 2021) and the GysBERT transformer embeddings (Arévalo & Fonteyn, 2022).

In the second phase, the best-performing method will be deployed across the entire Dutch Song Database to generate a dataset of floating stanzas. This dataset will enable further research on genre conventions, formulaic language and cultural circulation, potentially reshaping our understanding of the interplay between creativity and tradition in early modern song culture in the Low Countries.

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